

Justification of the reasons why Genre Mukhammas is not plagiarism.

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Annotation: The article analyzes five lines (mukhammas) in literature. The poets of various period, independent and takhmis compositions were studied, the weight and genre features of these poems, and the scope of the subject were examined. Takhmis related to the ghazals of Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Fuzuli and Nadira were also researched. The isolated part of Mukhammas belongs to the pen of Nadira, and the above three verses belong to Sabir Abdullah. Mukhammas has a special place in the poetry of the second half of the 20th century. Mukhammas is a poetic form consisting of 5 stanzas, in which all the lines of the first stanza rhyme with each other: in the following stanzas, the previous four stanzas rhyme with each other, and the fifth stanza rhymes with the first stanza. Mukhammas is taken from the Arabic word "hamsa" and means five or five. Each verse, the couplet of which consists of five lines, and in the first couplet all lines are built in one composition, and the other sections of the first four lines separately, and the fifth line rhymes with the first line of the first section, this is called mukhammas. This genre is divided into two according to the nature of creation:

1. Independent (tabi khud) epics are created by a poet himself. In this case, the creator does not use another poet's poem as a basis, but creates a poem independently.

2. Takhmis - the author takes another poet's or sometimes his own ghazal as a basis and continues the same theme, while maintaining the weight, rhyme and radif, creates a quintet. Three verses are added to the top of each verse in the ghazal based on this.

Key words: Mukhammas, poet, plagiarism, genre, component, copyright.

The legal analysis of a work of literature should single out the artistic form of the work as its most important component. It is thanks to the art form that it has

long been noticed that all arts are related to each other - the musicality of the verse ... the harmony of color. However, this affinity does not prevent them from being independent, since each type of art has its own unique figurative structure, its own special means of expression. The art form is inviolable, not because, in the words of old and new proprietary theories, is the "property" of the author, but because it is inseparable from the work as a whole, and not to protect the art form means a rejection of the institution of copyright in general. The ability to single out an art form in the composition of the components of a work of art or literature is of great importance for a lawyer in cases where he has to resolve a dispute about plagiarism between the authors of literary and other works. In these disputes, one has to compare two works, the components of which partially coincide. This coincidence may lead a reviewer or judge, who is not familiar with the structure of the work, to erroneously conclude that plagiarism is present. A number of examples can show that the element of art form is not just an art history category, but also a legal criterion.

Mukhammas is common in Eastern poetry as a genre. In form, mukhammas is a five-verse line, where the first three lines are the verses of the poet who wrote the mukhammas, and the last two lines are a couplet - a bayt belonging to the poet whose poem served as the basis for writing the mukhammas. In essence, mukhammas is a co-creation, a new poem written based on a well-known work, which inspired the poet to comprehend and voice the thoughts and images of the author in a new way in the light of modern times, and therefore mukhammas is not plagiarism and is considered an object of copyright.

Analyzing the genre of MUKHAMMAS in detail, it arose from the Arabic word "fivefold" - a strophic form in the poetry of the Near and Middle East, as well as among some peoples of the Caucasus (for example, among the Armenians - mkuhammaz). Each stanza of mukhammas has 5 verses. The verses of the first stanza have a common rhyme or a common redif. The second and subsequent stanzas have their own rhyme or redif for all lines, except for the final one, which necessarily ends with a rhyme or redif of the first stanza (and sometimes repeats the last verse of the first stanza in its entirety). Among the famous poets who used mukhammas: Mirza Asadullah Khan Galib; Bahadur Shah. This genre is divided into two by the nature of creation:

1. Independent (tabi hud) epics are created by the poet himself. In this case,

the creator does not take as a basis the poem of another poet, but creates a poem on his own.

2. Presumably, the author takes another poet's ghazal as a basis, and sometimes his own, continues the same theme and creates a quintet, preserving weight, rhyme and root. Based on this, three verses are added to the beginning of each verse in the ghazal. In a laudatory clause (16, 143), the nickname of the poet is also given, to whom takhmys is attributed. Alisher Navoi is a poet who developed takhmys in our literature. Both types of this genre were widely used in the works of poets of the second half of the 20th century. The works of Habibiy, Sabir Abdullah and Chusti were written in the measurements of the weight of aruz: Ramal, Khazaj, Mutakarib, Rajaz, Muzori, Mujtass, Khafif Bahri.

As can be seen from the above, the strophic form of mukhammas in Uzbek poetry of the 20th century was quite common. In mukhammas (five lines), written by poets at the beginning of the 20th century, there is an expansion of the thematic range, a search for new forms. The mukhammas of the famous satirist Mirza Alekber Sabir (1862–1911) begin with a couplet, which ends the stanzas of five lines. There are other innovations as well. Mukhammas are written on lyrical love, patriotic, socio-political, philosophical, religious and other topics. In a number of patriotic mukhammas, the beauties of the native land are praised. Some of them are dedicated to the defense of the homeland from invaders. The growth in the number of satirical mukhammas attracts attention. In general, mukhammas were widely used for the artistic reflection of many topical social problems, since they had enough opportunities for this. To this day, the genre of mukhammas attracts the attention of artists of the word, since it has great opportunities to give certain events and facts depicted a public sound.

The mukhammas genre has existed for many centuries, and every poet in the East dreams of writing mukhammas to the verses of his favorite poet and teacher. Mukhammas is a real test of the maturity of the poet's talent, a manifestation of his love for the author of the ghazal. Beautiful mukhammas were written by all poets, including Navoi and Jaami. According to many well-known Navoi scholars in Uzbekistan and abroad, including Ibrahim Khakkul and Sul-tonmurod Olim, mukhammas Jamol Kamol on Alisher Navoiy's brilliant poem "Asru" was a success. Jamol Kamol is a famous poet and a phenomenal translator from many world languages into Uzbek of such powerful works as: Rumi "Masnavi Manaviy"

from 6 books, Farididdin Attar from three books, Jaami more than 200 ghazals from Farsi-Tajik, Radiy Fish novel "Rumi" and other works from Russian, Shakespeare's 12 dramatic works from English are currently at the height of their spiritual and intellectual power and generally recognized poetic talent.

Based on the foregoing, the art form is not only a condition for the emergence of an object of copyright, but along with this it is a legal criterion for the application of copyright laws and there can hardly be any fundamental doubts that the art form of a work is not only an art criticism category, but also a carrier legal qualities that characterize the object of copyright. Analyzing the compared works in disputes about plagiarism, we come to the conclusion that the Mukhammas genre is not plagiarism and is subject to copyright.